

Artificial Intelligence: The Future of Communication?

Darnish Manjunath

3rd Semester BBA , Reva University

Dilip CV

3rd Semester BBA , Reva University

OPEN ACCESS

Volume : 6

Special Issue : 1

Month : August

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2321-788X

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Manjunath, Darnish, and Dilip CV. “Artificial Intelligence: The Future of Communication?”

Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humanities, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 56–58.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1403579>

Abstract

With the invent of computers there was always a doubt for human kinds future existence. As the years passed and technology progressed that very question of existence has come to a huge reach. But why not talk of co-existence? Social Media and Digital Market of the future will solely depend on the future AI as it's next best thing. With the rapid progress in technology and with the change of modern society will have to depend on AI for smooth operation.

Digitalisation has already been made a huge part of our life and we depend on it for a easier life. AI has already started to take its place in our lives. This paper will be talking about how and if AI can or cannot co-exist with respect to the marketing sector in an organization.

In this paper the authors make an attempt to present a conceptual over view of AI and it's impact on various areas of marketing by analysing various journals and published materials on the emergence of artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, digitalisation, marketing , co-existence, future, development, deep learning, internet .

Introduction

When we think of artificial intelligence we think about robots, but in reality artificial intelligence refers to an intelligent system that uses an algorithm so as to perform any mathematical computation. Artificial intelligence is a big field and we have tried to explore the full breadth of the field. Artificial intelligence marketing is a method of leveraging customer data and AI concepts like machine learning to predict the customer's next move and the improve the customer journey and fulfill the needs of the customer.

In the Information age more evolved systems are noticed day by day. The search for highly informational and personalized content are very difficult and there's a high demand for every social network. Artificial intelligence has been introduced to people in many forms and especially in movies, even though the films belong to science fiction the explanations given in the scripts about the creation of these machines are based on the general concept of machine intelligence which imitates the human brain. Artificial intelligence is basically Man Vs. Machine, and artificial intelligence started as a field whose

goal was to replicate the human level intelligence and replace the AI in place of humans. But the ever progressing technology, it's tough to expect what the next big move or thing that AI can achieve. Each developer or coder thinks in a completely different angle even when working on the same grounds. It's upto the person developing the program and the person writing the algorithm to use their innovation along with pre planned information and data to write the most acceptable code for grounds in AI for public use while making sure that the bridge or barrier between human and machine isn't breached.

Digitization

In the 1950's the word digitalization took the organisations by a whole new sweep. It opened up the world to a whole new way of saving , searching and recalling of memory and downloading, it showed people how they could save any form of information on remote disks and computers which in turn could be accessed by anyone , anywhere in the world irrespective of the geological conditions. Even though it was still in its beta stages , we knew that it would somehow show us the way to a faster and more innovative future. A future that not only be dreamt about but could be experienced to. In todays day and age, digitization has gone a long way compared to back when it was invented. Today, anyone can gain access to any information anywhere with or without the pain of going through or long wait process. The future of digitization with respect to Artificial Intelligent is something that everyone is looking forward to, as with every coming day some aspect of organization is being invented and there much easier ways to get the work done. Digitization has not only proven that things could get easier but it has also proven that the future may not be that far away as we thought.

Deep Learning

The aspects of deep learning can be traced straight to Artificial Intelligence because the way Ai works is how it can learn from past experiences of human behaviour and trace the current doings to predict the future and have the human wants and needs set before hand. That is what Aritificial Intelligerence is all about. As seen before, the main core ground of what AI is based upon is digitization as it collects data to to predict the future. Which we can call as Deep Learning. The main idea behind AI is to compile this data and to help the computers to give us humans the appropriate need for the moment. Some might call this data mining but that is what Ai is all about.

Co-existence

With AI people only talk about the future tech taking over human kind and it taking over human beings as a species. Everywhere we look and every person we speak to, they only talk about how AI is harmful to our species and how we while planning up new directions for technology might also result in the harm to our race. Everyone always talk about the bad of AI with admittedly a little bit of good. But why not co-existence? AI is as smart as we design it to be. We as humans can rely on AI for our day to day work but we might even be already be using it with our social media browsing and to run our media centers. The day is not far where we will have to co exist with AI and when we do, it will help our organisations in the field of marketing. For marketing a product we now have multiple people carrying out immense amount of research while expending a lot of time doing so. With the help of Ai we can get the researched data at a click away and know the markets wants and needs without expending a lot of time. The amount of work done in a set amount of time can have better smaller ratios yielding better results without having to worry about the conundrum of fact checking.

Internet

We know when artificial intelligence and internet get together they will transform both the Internet and Global economy in a very limited time . Artificial intelligence plays an important role in internet of things applications and developments. All the companies and start ups that combine with artificial intelligence and internet of things have become successful and have come up in the past few years . Big organisations across industries are already exploring the power of artificial intelligence and internet of things to deliver and to work efficiently in an organization . India is one of the countries where a lot of innovation and creativity is happening around internet of things across different verticals and technologies. Artificial intelligence can give lots of data meaning with respect to creating models and the concepts . Technology will become a part of everyday life even more and it has already become a part of everyone’s life. Artificial intelligence also helps to create web design and development. With more and more start ups coming to light with the help of artificial intelligence it is sure that the government might open up its funding and promote artificial intelligence for the country and to help maintain the governing bodies . When these governing bodies and start ups come together they help our country grow in aspects where no one has yet touched upon and it helps to grow the country’s economy and opens a whole new sector. With make in India initiative in full swing and we are sure that the future governing bodies will one day rely on artificial intelligence . That day is not far.

Marketing

Marketing in an organization is a pain staking process for the research team as they have to spend a lot time, money and energy in learning what the market response to a particular product would be and to learn the next market needs. With Ai working hand in hand with humans in an organization, the research and the prediction of future market needs gets easier and this in turn helps the organization reach its goals much easier and much earlier than the expected time frame. When an organization has an integrated Ai team working hand in hand to achieve goals, it helps them have a clear edge over the competing organization who have only individuals working on a project. It helps the organization to progress ahead without wasting time and to get the work done.

Future

With the rapid progress in the field of Ai, we cannot expect the future of the same. The organizations that have already started to adapt and work side by side with AI have shown that technology has and been progressing day by day. It helps in developing AI to a whole new level as it learns new information everyday. It is with this that AI grows and adapts with new information.

Conclusion

With all these rapid progress we can be sure that the future isn’t too far away and that Ai can soon help in all organizations. It is only a matter of time until AI helps in all the aspects in an organization and the future grows by leaps and bounds.